

Electrometric Studies on Clay-humic Acid Interactions

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The interactions between H-clays (original and oxide-free) and humic acid fraction (HA) of soil humus have been studied by electrometric titrations.

Conductometric studies show the formation of four different types of complexes with original clay and three different types with clay (oxide-free) fractions. Potentiometric studies support these findings.

It is an established fact that soil organic matter fractions are capable of interacting with clays to form complexes. Mechanisms of such reactions have been reviewed by Mortland¹ and Greenland².

In the present paper some attempts have been made to give information on the nature of interactions between clay and humic acid fractions employing electrometric methods.

Experimental

Organic matter was extracted and fractionated from Bigra Pond Sediment, Dist. Burdwan, W.B (0-15 cm depth) by the procedure adopted by Banerjee and Mukherjee³. The humic acid (HA) thus fractionated was dialysed and finally electro-dialysed.

After removal of organic matter from the sediment, it was treated with H_2O_2 to remove the residual organic matter. The excess H_2O_2 was removed by warming it to 80-90° in water bath. The clay-fractions ($<2\mu$) were collected from this by the usual process of dispersion and sedimentation. The clay isolated was treated with dil HCl to convert it to H-clay which was then purified by dialysis. Finally these dialysed H-clay materials were shaken with a cation exchange resin (Amberlite I-R-120 in the H-form) to get the H-clay. For preparation of oxide-free clay, the procedure as adopted by Mehra and Jackson⁴ was followed which was subsequently converted in H-form.

Conductometric Titration: In a number of stoppered 10 ml volumetric flasks, fixed amount of clay and increasing amounts of HA solutions were added. The contents of these flasks were shaken for 12 hrs and allowed to equilibrate for 7-8 days. The total volume was made up to 10 ml in each case. After equilibrium conductances of the solutions were measured by Leeds-Northrup conductivity bridge at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. Conductometric titrations of HA fraction and HA-clay combinations with NaOH were also carried out.

Potentiometric Titration: Compositions of the complexes were determined from the inflexion points of conductometric titration curves as shown in Fig. 1(a). From this knowledge different complex species were prepared by mixing clay and HA in different complex species were prepared by mixing clay and HA in different mole ratios. These were titrated with NaOH solution in Cambridge pH-meter at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.

The conductometric and potentiometric titration curves of H-clay-HA, H-clay (oxide-free)-HA and their complexes are shown in Figs. 1(b, c, d and e).

Fig. 1(a).

Fig. 1(b)

Fig. 1(c).

Fig. 1(d).

Fig. 1(e).

Results and Discussion

The average molecular weight of the electrodialysed HA and the clay were found by electrometric

method⁵ to be 2,000 and 30,000 respectively. The present discussions are based on such results.

Instantaneous conductometric titrations (curve not shown) of HA with H-clay (original and oxide-free) are of continuous nature showing no complex formation. But discontinuous titration (after equilibration), shows four inflexion points for original clay-HA and three for clay (oxide-free)-HA titrations, indicating complex formation at these points, Fig. 1(a). The molal compositions corresponding to the original clay-HA are 1 : 5, 1 : 12.5, 1 : 25 and 1 : 40 and clay (oxide-free)-HA are 1 : 5, 1 : 37.2 and 1 : 42.5 respectively.

The conductometric titration of HA by caustic alkali show two breaks [Fig. 1(b)]. It also follows from conductometric titration of clay-HA system, the conductance of the solution depends on the number, the charge and the mobility of the ions present. Some of the characteristic points from the conductometric titration curves of clay-HA system can be described as follows :

(1) The low conductance at the point X [Fig. 1(b and e)] is attributable to the neutralization of hydroxyl ions by the H⁺ ions which had previously been adsorbed in the clay-HA system. The very low dissociation of the cation from polyanion complex also contributes to the observation of very low conductance value.

(2) At the point Y [Fig. 1(b and e)] the conductivity of the "free base" determines the further course of the titration curve with a constant slope.

It also appears from conductometric titration systems, the adsorption of HA on clay-surfaces depends on cleavage of the hydrogen-bridge linkage between carboxyl and hydroxyl groups of the adjacent molecules of humic acids and more the adsorption the clay-HA systems tend to disperse. This corroborates with the view of Halla and Ruston⁶.

The distinctive nature of conductometric titration curves of original clay, clay (oxide-free) and their complexes with HA indicate that sesqui-oxides present in soil clays play important role in the interaction between clays and organic compounds. From the increasing trend of conductance values of clay-HA complexes with caustic alkali, it may be inferred that there is a possibility of formation of 'water-bridge like compounds'¹ linking polymeric HA molecules to the exchangeable metal cations of the clay surface as :

where M^{n+} is the metal cation and $-COOH$ is one of the functional groups of HA. On interaction with NaOH, Na^+ exchanges for polyvalent ions, such as Ca^{+2} , Mg^{+2} , Fe^{+3} etc., present on the clay surface. A fresh claysol-HA product does not show any distinct change in conductance measurements but the product on ageing actually changes to H-Al-clay system^{7,8}.

Potentiometric titration curve of HA, original clay-HA complexes with standard alkali are shown in Fig. 1(d and e). During the titration of original clay with NaOH, the change of pH is initially slow, indicating an weak acidity. But after that, the nature of the curve begins to flatten. This may be due to accumulation of osmotically active Na^+ ions in the mobile double layer of the clay surface, replacing the surface H^+ ions of the clay.

From the Fig. 1(d and e) it is seen that the lesser amounts of alkali is required for neutralization of HA than is needed to titrate clay-organic complexes which is due to uncoiling (unfolding) effect of HA after adsorption on clay surfaces, necessitating more alkali for neutralization of active groups. Similar observation was made by Alexandrova⁹ in studying metal HA chelates as stated in Gieseking¹⁰.

In order to get an idea about the mechanism of clay-HA interactions, the number of proton released from organic matter by addition of clay are assessed and shown in Table 1. From the data given in Table 1, it is evident that the number of protons

From this study it is inferred that clay-HA complexes are more or less stable up to a pH 7 to 8 and above which they begin to break up, resulting in release of larger number of protons¹¹. It is noticed that in both clay (oxide) and clay (oxide-free)-HA complexes number of proton released at lower pH ranges is much less than unity in most cases.

Hence it may be inferred that HA may have penetrated into the co-ordination shell of the surface hydroxyl layer of the clay in such a way that it is not sensitive to pH change. Similar views were expressed by Edward and Bremner¹².

Furthermore, from the pH titration it appears that the nature of the curves are alike at the lower pH-range, irrespective of nature of clay system used, i.e., original or oxide-free. At pH 3.5 the differences of the titration properties of the clay ions are small, because at this pH-value the clay ions are still in a undissociated state in solution.

It is thus concluded that the linkage between HA and clay ions is of covalent character or formation of water bridge like compounds¹ which conforms to the views of Van Dijk¹³, Khanna and Stevenson¹⁴.

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TABLE 1—NUMBER OF PROTONS RELEASED FROM HA/mole OF CLAY ADDED

pH	H-clay : HA complexes in mole ratio			
	1 : 5	1 : 12.5	1 : 25	1 : 40
4.0	0.22	0.24	0.5	0.27
4.5	0.26	0.34	0.52	0.28
5.0	0.32	0.38	0.58	0.32
5.5	0.36	0.42	0.74	0.58
6.0	0.52	0.48	0.90	0.60
6.5	0.58	0.52	0.92	0.62
7.0	0.62	0.56	0.94	0.66
7.5	0.64	0.60	1.08	0.72
8.0	0.76	0.64	1.16	0.80
8.5	0.82	0.70	1.28	0.86
9.0	1.02	—	1.56	0.92
9.5	1.10	—	1.60	1.04
10.0	—	0.86	1.80	1.20

released from organic matter increases with pH in all the clay-HA systems.

It is thus evident that higher the concentration of organic matter, greater is the number of protons released and the maximum number of protons released is approximately 2 in the case of complex having molar composition of clay : HA = 1 : 25.

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